

Simple monitoring of cancer cells using nanoparticles

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Here we present a new strategy for a simple and fast detection of cancer circulating cells (CTCs) using nanoparticles. Human Colon Adenocarcinoma Cell line (Caco2) was chosen as a model CTC. Similarly to other adenocarcinomas, colon adenocarcinoma cells have a strong expression of EpCAM and for this reason this glycoprotein was used as the capture target. We combine the capturing capability of anti-EpCAM functionalized magnetic beads (MBs) and the specific labeling through antibody-modified gold nanoparticles (AuNPs), with the sensitivity of the AuNPs-electrocatalyzed Hydrogen Evolution Reaction (HER) detection technique. The fully optimized process was used for the electrochemical detection of Caco2 cells in presence of monocytes (THP-1), other circulating cells that could interfere in real blood samples. Therefore we obtained a novel and simple in situ-like sensing format that we applied for the rapid quantification of AuNPs-labeled CTCs in presence of other human cells.

KEYWORDS: Nanobiosensor; Cancer detection; Immunosensing; Gold nanoparticles; Hydrogen evolution reaction; electrocatalysis.

Circulating Tumor Cells (CTCs) are traveling cells in physiological fluids which are released from a main tumor or from metastasis. CTCs quantification is of great interest for evaluating cancer dissemination, predicting patient prognosis, and also for the evaluation of therapeutic treatments.¹⁻³ representing a reliable potential alternative to invasive biopsies and subsequent proteomic and functional genetic analysis.^{4,5} In fact, isolation of CTCs from peripheral blood, as a ‘liquid biopsy’, is expected to be able to complement conventional tissue biopsies of metastatic tumors for therapy guidance.^{1,6} A particularly important aspect of a ‘liquid biopsy’ is that it is safe and can be performed frequently, because repeated invasive procedures may be responsible for limited sample accessibility.⁷ The main techniques reported for CTC detection consist in their labeling with tagged antibodies (immunocytometry) followed by fluorescence analysis, or the detection of the expression of tumor markers by reverse-transcriptase polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR).⁸ However, the required previous isolation of CTCs from the human fluids is limited to complex analytic approaches that often result in a low yield and purity.^{9,10}

Cancer cells overexpress specific proteins at their plasma membrane, being these proteins often used as targets in CTCs sensing methodologies using the information available for the different types of cancer cells.¹¹ One relevant protein is the Epithelial Cell Adhesion Molecule (EpCAM), a 30-40 kDa type I glycosylated membrane protein which is expressed in a low extent in many human epithelial tissues but is overexpressed in most solid carcinomas.¹² EpCAM has a relevant role in tumorigenesis and has also been identified as a cancer stem cell marker in a variety of solid cancers. For example, it has been found in more than 98% of colorectal adenocarcinomas, being its expression inversely related to the prognosis.^{13,14} Another example of a tumor associated protein is the Carcinoembryonic antigen (CEA), a 180-200 kDa highly glycosylated cell surface glycoprotein which overexpression was originally thought to be specific for human colon adenocarcinomas.

Nowadays it is known to be associated with other tumors, and the large variations of serum CEA levels and CEA expression by disseminated tumor cells have been strongly correlated with the tumor size, its state of differentiation, the degree of invasiveness and the extent of metastatic spread.^{14,15}

The objective of this work is to develop a rapid electrochemical biosensing strategy for CTCs quantification using specific antibodies labelled with gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) and magnetic beads (MBs) capture platforms in liquid suspensions. AuNPs have been reported are excellent labels in both optical (e.g. ELISA) and electrochemical (e.g. differential pulse voltammetric) detection of DNA¹⁶ and proteins.^{17,18} The use of the electrocatalytic properties of the AuNPs on hydrogen formation from hydrogen ions (Hydrogen Evolution Reaction, HER) also enables an enhanced quantification of nanoparticles¹⁹ allowing the detection, of even proteins of clinical interesting human serum samples through their labeling with nanoparticle conjugates.²⁰ We also reported HER reaction to be very useful in the detection of the human tumor HMy2 cell line (HLA-DR class II positive B cells) in the presence of another human tumor PC-3 cell line (HLA-DR class II negative prostate carcinoma) while being immobilized onto a carbon electrode platform.²¹

Since human fluid samples are complex and contain a variety of cells and metabolites, the fast detection of CTCs becomes quite a difficult task. To get through this obstacle, several attempts of filtration, pre-concentration or other purification steps are actually being reported by researchers that work in this field and each of them has advantages and drawbacks.^{22,23} The only FDA (U.S. Food and Drug Administration) approved method for the detection of CTCs is the Cell Search System® that first enriches the tumor cells immunomagnetically by means of ferrofluidic nanoparticles conjugated to EpCAM and then, after immunomagnetic capture and enrichment, allows the identification and enumeration of CTCs using fluorescent staining.^{24,25} When sample processing is complete, images are presented to the user in a

gallery format for final cell classification. However, this imaging based analysis of individual cells is time-consuming and but also expensive due to the cost of both fluorescent labels and the equipment required for their monitoring. In order to overcome these drawbacks we design and evaluate in this work an electrochemical detection system based on the electrocatalytic properties of AuNPs labels, in combination with the use of superparamagnetic microparticles (MBs) modified with anti-EpCAM as a cell capture agent (Figure 1). The integration of both systems, the capture with MBs and the labeling with electrocatalytic AuNPs, should provide a selective and sensitive method for the detection and quantification of CTCs in liquid suspensions.

The human colon adenocarcinoma cell line Caco2, was chosen as a model CTC. Similarly to other adenocarcinomas, colon adenocarcinoma cells, show a strong expression of EpCAM (close to 100%)¹² and for this reason this glycoprotein was used as the capture target. In relation to AuNPs labeling, we explored two different protein targets: EpCAM and CEA, both expressed by Caco2 cells. Two separate electrochemical detections were performed, each one using a different antibody conjugated to AuNPs, in order to choose the one that achieves a better electrochemical response in terms of both sensitivity and selectivity.

The biofunctionalized electrochemical labels were prepared by conjugation of AuNPs (20 nm sized prepared using Turkevich's citrate capped modified synthesis²⁶) with rabbit polyclonal anti-EpCAM antibody or mouse monoclonal anti-CEA antibody following a previously optimized protocol.²⁰ These 20 nm sized AuNPs have previously shown an excellent electrocatalytic activity, being also easily synthesized, bioconjugated and purified¹⁹⁻²¹. The nanoparticles were characterized by Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) and also UV/Vis absorbance spectroscopy, to check both the size distribution and the presence of the antibody layer around them after biofunctionalization. We observed a mean size of 19.2 ± 1.4 nm and a typical maximum of absorbance at 520 nm that shifted to 529 nm after

biofunctionalization (see Figure S1 at the *Supporting Information*). This red shift in the absorbance is explained by the changes in the AuNPs-surface plasmon resonance, indicating a different composition of the surface and evidencing the formation of the conjugate.

To assess the effectiveness of AuNPs/antibody-conjugate labels, their specific interaction with Caco2 cells in suspension was evaluated. With this aim, fluorescence microscopy imaging of cell samples before and after incubation with biofunctionalized AuNPs, using a fluorescent tagged secondary antibody, was performed. The free anti-EpCAM antibody proved to have high affinity for EpCAM at Caco2 surface (data not shown), but it was necessary to verify that after conjugation with AuNPs the antibody maintains its ability to recognize the target protein. The resulting fluorescence at the cell membrane (Figure 2) confirmed the specific biorecognition of the Caco2 cells by the AuNPs/anti-EpCAM. This fact was also evidenced by flow cytometry analysis of the cell samples. Flow cytometry is well suited to check the affinity of different antibodies to several cell proteins and, by using the proper controls, it can also be used to quantify both labeled and unlabeled cells. Using the same protocol for sample preparation as for optical microscopy, Caco2 samples were analyzed (Figure 3). When the cells were labeled with AuNPs/rabbit-anti-EpCAM-conjugate, followed by a fluorescent secondary anti-rabbit antibody, a strong increase in cell fluorescence was observed (Figure 3a). Several controls were performed for both methods. Caco2 cells were incubated with rabbit-anti-EpCAM antibody both free and conjugated to AuNPs. Controls were also performed with AuNPs/anti-EpCAM without fluorescent-tagged secondary antibody (see Figure S2a at the *Supporting Information*), and with AuNPs conjugated to another rabbit polyclonal anti-EpCAM antibody that proved to be non-specific to Caco2 cells (see Figure S2b at the *Supporting Information*).

For the magnetic capture of Caco2, we first used 4.5 μm MBs conjugated to a monoclonal anti-EpCAM antibody. Although 4.5 μm MBs are generally used for cell applications, due to

their large size and high magnetic mobility, our experiments with anti-EpCAM functionalized 4.5 μm MBs resulted in discrepancies both in flow cytometry analysis and electrochemical detection. After MBs and AuNPs incubation, Caco2 cells seemed damaged and/or agglomerated when analyzed by fluorescence microscopy and flow cytometry (see Figure S3, S4 and S5 at the *Supporting Information*). This damage may be due to the large size of these MBs, which promotes higher flow-induced shear stress during the cleaning steps performed with stirring.^{27,28} Since CTCs are reported to be vulnerable cells which viability is easily compromised after capture,⁶ we tested smaller MBs (tosylactivated 2.8 μm) that are recommended for extremely fragile cells, due to their smaller size and lower magnetophoretic mobility, and can reduce the possibility of interference between the nearest particles.²⁹ These are uniform polystyrene beads (with a magnetic core), coated with a polyurethane layer modified with sulphonyl ester groups, that can subsequently react covalently with proteins or other ligands containing amino or sulfhydryl groups. MBs were functionalized with a monoclonal anti-EpCAM antibody previously tested by flow cytometry analysis. The electrochemical measurements and the cytometry analyses were in agreement: these MBs can capture the cells without perceived damage (Figure 3b and 3c) and allow for better electrochemical results. We also evaluated MBs with smaller diameters (200 nm) but with unsatisfactory results (data not shown) probably due to the fact that the magnets used for the magnetic cleaning steps were not powerful enough to capture these small MBs, which resulted in the loss of the cells during the referred steps, so the 2.8 μm sized were used for all the experiments detailed below.

We also performed optimization of the ratio MBs/cell, as well as the cell incubation sequence with both MBs/anti-EpCAM and AuNPs/anti-EpCAM conjugates to improve the AuNPs electrochemical signal. The MBs/cell and AuNPs/cell ratios used in the detection assay are very important, since MBs/anti-EpCAM quantity must be lower enough to allow the

maximum labeling efficiency by AuNPs/anti-EpCAM conjugate that will in turn give the detection signal. Regarding the incubation sequence with conjugates, if a separate incubation is performed using MBs/anti-EpCAM in the first place, the EpCAM at the cell surface could be “blocked” for the further labeling with AuNPs/anti-EpCAM, resulting in a loss of AuNPs electrochemical signal. In the case that a simultaneous incubation is performed, both MBs and AuNPs conjugates compete for the same protein and consequently, the aforementioned blocking effect could also occur. To test this, several ratios of MBs conjugates (1:1, 2:1, 4:1 and 14:1 MBs/cell), using two incubation protocols (MBs/anti-EpCAM and AuNPs/anti-EpCAM simultaneous and separate incubations) were evaluated. Flow cytometry results (see Fig. S5 at the *Supporting Information*) showed that a high MB/cell ratio is associated not only to more cell damage/death (cells are exposed to a higher magnetic attraction) but also to a higher number of cells without the MBs/anti-EpCAM. Therefore, it seems that an excess of MBs/anti-EpCAM (14:1 MBs/cell) is not favorable to the detection, and the best results were achieved with a 2:1 MBs/cell ratio. It is also important to clarify that when MBs/anti-EpCAM were not used (only AuNPs/anti-EpCAM labeling) the flow cytometry analysis reported 98% of AuNPs/anti-EpCAM-labeled cells with a low value of dead cells. This result was obtained for cells incubated with a large excess of AuNPs/anti-EpCAM ($\sim 9 \times 10^{10}$ AuNPs) (see Fig. S6a at the *Supporting Information*), which leads to the conclusion that, contrary to MBs/anti-EpCAM, an excess of AuNPs/anti-EpCAM does not affect cell integrity, probably due to their smaller size. Finally, concerning the incubation sequence, we chose the simultaneous one as the optimal in order to obtain a fast capture/labeling of cells with both conjugates (see Fig. S6b at the *Supporting Information*). Moreover, when using the 2:1 MBs/cell ratio the flow cytometry analysis did not indicate major differences between the two tested incubations (both were done using an AuNPs/MBs ratio of 9×10^5).

The accurate study of the Caco2 cell-biofunctionalized AuNP interaction is very important to elucidate the specificity and selectivity of the sensing system presented here. The use of scanning electron microscopy (SEM) is a well-known characterization technique for cells with relative large dimensions. However, its application in the case of cells interaction with small nanometer sized materials in liquid suspension is not an easy task. Cells often lack the requirements of structure stability and electron conductivity necessary for high magnification SEM images, and it is usually necessary to cover the entire sample with a nano/micro layer of conductive material. This metallization process will mask the small nanoparticles attached to the cell surface. Therefore, we adapted a SEM sample preparation protocol to fulfill two requirements: the cells should always be kept in suspension, so that the characterization is done in exactly the same conditions than the electrochemical detection, and no sample coating should be performed, to avoid the masking of AuNPs/anti-EpCAM that should be present at the cell surface. Accordingly, cell samples were kept in suspension while treated with glutaraldehyde fixative with subsequent dehydration solutions, and finally resuspended in hexamethyldisilazane (HMDS) solution prior to the drop-deposition onto a silicon dioxide wafer. No metal-oxides were used and the critical-point drying procedure was not performed nor the final metallization step. HMDS is generally used in photolithography techniques, as an adhesion promoter between silicon dioxide films and the photoresist. However, in the present method, HMDS is used as a substitute of the critical-point, as it is reported to be a time-saving alternative without introducing additional artifacts in SEM images.^{30,31} We processed samples in which Caco2 cells were incubated in the presence or absence of AuNPs/anti-EpCAM conjugate.

With the optimized SEM preparation protocol and the Field Emission-SEM (FE-SEM) precise technical settings, we obtained high quality images (Figure 4a). At high magnification we could see the detail of the plasma membrane and using the Backscattered Electrons mode

(BSE) we could discriminate the small AuNPs attached onto the Caco2 cell membrane through the immunoreaction (Figure 4b). Since heavy elements backscatter electrons more strongly than light elements, they appear brighter in the obtained image, thus enhancing the contrast between objects of different chemical compositions. In addition, as we did not use metal-oxides during the fixation of cells, the only metal-origin element in the samples should be the gold from the AuNPs used as labels. When the same procedure was performed for monocytes (Figure 4c and d), no AuNPs were observed, demonstrating the specificity of the AuNPs anti-EpCAM.

We processed other samples in which Caco2 cells were mixed with the THP-1 control cells in a 70% Caco2 and 30% THP-1 proportion, and then incubated with MBs/anti-EpCAM with and without labeling of AuNPs/anti-EpCAM. As expected, no monocytes were found in the SEM sample (Figure 5) since they were supposed to be removed during the magnetic separation steps. At higher magnification, using the BSE mode (Figure 5c and d), the presence of AuNPs/anti-EpCAM dispersed onto the Caco2 surface could be observed. Several membrane protrusions were also observed in all the SEM images when MBs/anti-EpCAM were used as capture conjugates (Figure 5b). These are finger like structures that epithelial cells can develop in cell-matrix adherent processes³²⁻³⁴ and in which Ep-CAM can also be involved.^{34,35} It is important to note that these protrusions are enhanced when MBs are used (see Figure S8 at the *Supporting Information*), whereas in the samples of Caco2 and Caco2- labeled only with AuNPs/anti-EpCAM (see Figure S7 at the *Supporting Information*) the cell structure seems well confined. Although this evidence is not directly related to the assay performance, we believe these effects may be related to the different sizes of MBs and AuNPs, being MBs approximately 1.4×10^3 times larger.

The fully optimized process was used for the electrochemical detection of Caco2 cells in presence of monocytes (THP-1), other circulating cells that could interfere in real blood

samples. The use of the electrocatalytic properties of the AuNPs on hydrogen formation from hydrogen ions (HER) makes it possible to quantify the AuNPs and, in turn, to quantify the corresponding labeled cancer cells (through the proteins to which these are connected).¹⁹ Chronoamperometric plotting of the analytical signal is much simpler, from signal acquisition point of view, than the stripping analysis or differential pulse voltammetry described in previous works.^{16,17} To evaluate the selectivity of the assays, Caco2 cells were mixed with the THP-1 control cells in different proportions, and then incubated with both MB/anti-EpCAM and AuNPs/anti-EpCAM in a one-step incubation. After magnetic separation and cleaning steps, the samples were analyzed following the electrocatalytic method explained. Samples with 100%, 70%, 50% and 20% of Caco2 cells (Figure 6a) were tested (100% corresponds to 5×10^4 cells) in the presence of THP-1 cells, demonstrating that this method is selective for Caco2 cells. A linear relationship between the cells number and the value of the analytical signal in the range of 1×10^4 - 5×10^4 cells is obtained ($n=6$; data not shown) with a correlation coefficient (R) of 0.91. The limit of detection (LOD) calculated as the cells number corresponding to three times the standard deviation of the current value obtained for the blank assay (performed in the absence of Caco2 cells) was of 8.34×10^3 Caco2 cells. The reproducibility of the assay showed a relative standard deviation (RSD) of 4.92% for 5×10^4 cells ($n=10$). .. However, the achieved LOD is not enough to guarantee the application of the method. This is probably due to the aforementioned competition between antibody-modified MBs and AuNPs for the EpCAM protein. Furthermore, EpCAM is considered a general marker for a large variety of epithelial cells, so the selection of a more specific target was required to improve both the specificity and the sensitivity of the assay. Concretely, the CEA protein was chosen as it is reported to be strongly associated with the invasiveness of cancer cells, and it is known to be overexpressed by colon adenocarcinoma cells.^{14,15} The AuNPs were biofunctionalized with a mouse anti-CEA and used as

electrochemical labels. The incubation of Caco2 cells with the AuNPs/anti-CEA was done simultaneously with the capturing by MBs/anti-EpCAM followed by the electrocatalytic detection. The electrochemical analysis of Caco2 cells in the absence of THP-1 (n=6; Figure 6c) resulted in a linear range of 1×10^3 - 3.5×10^4 cells, with a R of 0.99, obtaining in this case a LOD, calculated as detailed before, of 1.6×10^2 cells, The RSD of 5.6 % for 5×10^4 cells (n=10), evidences a very good reproducibility of the results if we take into consideration that the number of nanoparticles attached to the cells due to the interaction between the antibody and CEA depends primarily on the number and distribution of the antigen molecule over the surface, which may vary from cell to cell and from batch to batch³⁶. The results obtained using AuNPs/anti-CEA as the detection labels were much better, in terms of LOD, than those with AuNPs/anti-EpCAM. When changing the AuNPs-conjugate antibody to anti-CEA the goal was to have better specificity in the detection without losing the sensitivity. Consequently, the AuNPs/anti-CEA was also tested for the electrochemical detection of Caco2 cells in the presence of THP-1 control cells (Figure 6b). Caco2 cells were mixed with THP-1 in different proportions (100, 70, 50, 20% of Caco2 cells; 100% corresponds to 5×10^4 cells) and then incubated with both MB/anti-EpCAM and AuNPs/anti-CEA in a one-step incubation. After magnetic separation and cleaning steps, samples were analyzed by the same electrochemical procedure previously mentioned. The statistical analysis reported a LOD of 2.2×10^2 Caco2 cells, with a correlation coefficient of 0.968 in a linear range from 1×10^4 to 5×10^4 cells with RSD = 6.3% for 5×10^4 cells. This value is quite similar to that obtained in the absence of THP-1, evidencing the high selectivity obtained thanks to the CEA recognition together with the magnetic separation/purification.

The experimental results indicate that the use of nanoparticles as labeling agents in immunoassays results in an improvement of sensitivity over the traditional enzyme or dye based assays.³⁷ Nanometer-sized particles such as metal and iron-oxide nanoparticles display

optical, electrochemical, magnetic or structural properties that the materials in molecular or bulk state do not have. When these particles are conjugated with specific antibodies they can target tumor-expressed proteins with high affinity and specificity. For example, AuNPs of 20 nm diameter have large surface areas that promote a good conjugation to antibodies and provide a fast interaction with nanometer sized antigens at the cell surface. The labeled tumor cells can then be detected and quantified through the appropriate methods for AuNPs detection, which can be optical, electric or electrochemical. From the several methods available, the electrochemical routes hold several advantages related to the gold nanoparticles specific characteristics, such as their own redox properties and excellent electroactivity towards other reactions. Exploiting the latest, advantages can be taken from the electrocatalytic effect that AuNPs have over several reactions, which exclude the need for contact between the electrode surface and the nanoparticle³⁷, and is suitable when detecting particles used as labels for relatively large dimensions such as the tumor cells.

The electrochemical detection of metal nanoparticles in general, and AuNPs in particular, can be accomplished using simple and portable apparatus that do not require large volume samples, time-consuming steps or high skilled users if thinking on point of care applications. After optimization, the detection can be seen as a semi-automated technique that could be integrated in small lab-on-a-chip platforms with the additional improvements related to the required volumes and time of analysis inherent to these systems.³⁸

The developed CTC detection technology includes several parameter optimizations as for example the size of the magnetic particles, their functionalization with antibodies, or the specificity of the antibody used to functionalize the AuNPs labels, including other protocol related parameters (e.g. incubation times) and the respective parameters related to the characterization by microscopy (optical and electronic) and flow cytometry.

Using the technical advances in electron microscopy to better characterize the cell-nano and -microparticle interactions, we processed samples in which Caco2 cells were mixed with THP-1 control cells (other circulating cells which could interfere in real blood samples) and were then incubated with AuNPs/anti-EpCAM and MB/anti-EpCAM conjugates. Using the Backscattered Electrons mode (BSE) mode we confirmed the presence of AuNPs/anti-EpCAM all around the Caco2 cell surface, whereas no monocytes were present in the sample. These observations proved that the capture and labeling with anti-EpCAM-functionalized particles is selective for Caco2 cells and thus a specific detection of target cells in the presence of other circulating cells can be achieved.

The full-optimized process was used for the electrochemical detection of Caco2 cells in the presence of THP-1. Although the results proved that the method was selective for Caco2 cells, the achieved limit of detection was not enough to guarantee the application of the method. The fact that the capture and detection labels were oriented to the same target protein, could hinder our detection due to the possible blocking effect that MBs could exert over the small AuNPs. For this reason, we believed that the detection could be improved using a different antibody in the detection-conjugated label, specific to other protein in the cell plasma membrane. To pursuit this goal, other antigens/proteins that are also present at Caco2 cells surface, and assumed to be relevant in the study/quantification of CTCs, were also considered. Since EpCAM is a general marker for a large variety of epithelial cells, another more specific detection using CEA as the target for the AuNPs-conjugate label was performed. We obtained better LOD values, in the absence and presence of other control cells, which are nearer the desirable for a valuable CTCs detection.

One of the possible explanations for the better results achieved is that in this case both MBs and AuNPs are not competing for the same antigen in the cell surface, maximizing in this way the number of AuNPs attached to the cell surface. Furthermore another factor which

could contribute to this achievement is that CEA is a much bigger protein than EpCAM (180kDa vs. 40kDa), so although both CEA and EpCAM are transmembrane proteins, the first one presents a larger extracellular domain, more similar in size to the antibody (150kDa). Even though the anti-CEA Fab fragment size, which is mainly responsible for the antigen recognition, has an equivalent size to the Fab' from anti-EpCAM, the possible steric effects related to the antigen size^{39,40} can help to elucidate why a better signal is obtained when using CEA as target at the cell membrane.

In summary, we have achieved the rapid and simple detection of cancer circulating cells using nanoparticles. The electrochemical detection and the characterization results demonstrate that this method is selective for Caco2 cells, and that the electrochemical signal is not affected by the presence of other circulating cells. The achieved detection through the AuNPs/anti-CEA conjugates is selective for the target tumor cells and can exclude the false positive results related to the EpCAM marker. The main advantages of the presented method, compared with the already reported for CTC detection (i.e. optical methods, ELISA, RT-CPR) rely on the sensitive and quantitative electrochemical detection technique used in addition to the excellent properties of the AuNPs labels. The sensitivity, simplicity, low cost, easy-to-use mode and miniaturization/portability of the electrochemical detection system makes it ideal for point-of-care applications. Furthermore, the use of AuNPs electrocatalytic labels gives rise to very simple electrochemical records that allow the rapid quantification of the cells in the sample.

We envision the application of the presented method to the quantification of CTCs in real human samples where besides cells (cancerous and non-cancerous ones), also proteins and metabolites are present. Although the anti-CEA antibody is not specific for CTCs (in fact, it can also recognize the CEA that is frequently found in the serum of patients with several types of cancer), its combination with MBs/anti-EpCAM provides a selective capture and

labeling of cells that express both antigens. This principle can also be adapted for other cancer cells by redesigning both micro- and nano-conjugates with the appropriate antibodies. Furthermore, the potential incorporation of the presented method for isolation, labeling and sensitive electrochemical detection/quantification of Caco2 cells in lab-on-a-chip systems^{3,41} could contribute to the desired standardization of CTCs detection technologies.

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION AVAILABLE

Materials and Methods, Figures S1 to S8 and proposal for a Cover Figure.

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Figure 1. Overall scheme. (a) Caco2 cells capture by MBs-anti-EpCAM and simultaneous labeling with AuNPs/specific antibodies in the presence of control cells; (b) Detection of labeled Caco2 cells through the Hydrogen Evolution Reaction (HER) electrocatalyzed by the AuNP labels. Right: Chronoamperograms registered in 1M HCl, during the HER applying a constant voltage of -1.0V, for AuNP labeled CaCo2 cells (3.5×10^4 - red curve) and for the blank (PBS/BSA - blue curve). Right: Comparison of the corresponding analytical signals (absolute value of the current registered at 50 seconds).

Figure 2. Fluorescence microscopy characterization. (a-c) Microscopy imaging of Caco2 cells in bright field (a, b, c), and fluorescence modes (a', b', c'). (a, a') Cells in suspension labeled with AuNPs/rabbit-anti-EpCAM (blue) and sequential labeling with FITC-conjugated secondary anti-rabbit antibody (green); (b, b') cells captured with MBs/mouse-anti-EpCAM (dark green) and simultaneous labeling with AuNPs/rabbit-anti-EpCAM (blue) showing the autofluorescence of MBs; (c, c') cells in the same conditions as in b after sequential labeling with FITC-conjugated secondary anti-rabbit antibody (green). Scale bar, 15 μm .

Figure 3. Flow Cytometry analysis performed after 30 minute incubations, as described in the methods section (see Supporting Information). After appropriate forward and sideward scatter gating, the Caco2 cells were evaluated using PE-A and APC-A signals. **(a)** Representative dot plots of Caco2 cells labeled with AuNPs/anti-EpCAM ; **(b)** Caco2 cells captured by MBs/anti-EpCAM; **(c)** Caco2 cells captured with MBs/anti-EpCAM and simultaneously labeled with AuNPs/anti-EpCAM. **(d)** Representative histogram count of Caco2 cells captured with MBs/anti-EpCAM, unlabeled (black) vs. labeled (red) with AuNPs/anti-EpCAM using the APC-conjugated secondary antibody.

Figure 4. Scanning electron microscopy. **(a)** SEM image (false colored with Corel Paint Shop Pro) of Caco2 cell incubated with AuNPs/anti-EpCAM conjugates; **(b)** Higher magnification image, using backscattered electrons mode, showing AuNPs distributed along the cell plasma membrane. **(c)** SEM image (false colored with Corel Paint Shop Pro) of control cell (THP-1); **(d)** Higher magnification image of THP-1 cell in backscattered electrons mode. Scale bars, 3 μm (**a** and **c**) and 200 nm (**b-d**).

Figure 5. Scanning electron microscopy. **(a-d)** Caco2 cells captured with MB/anti-EpCAM and simultaneously labeled with AuNPs/anti-EpCAM, in presence of THP-1 cells. **(a, b)** SEM images (false colored with Corel Paint Shop Pro) of a Caco2 cell captured by MBs/anti-EpCAM. **(c, d)** Higher magnification backscattered images of the Caco2 cell surface showing AuNPs distributed along the cell plasma membrane. Scale bars, 3 μm **(a)**, 400 nm **(b)** and 200 nm **(c, d)**.

Figure 6. Electrochemical detection of Caco2 cells using MBs/anti-EpCAM for selective capture. **(a, b)** Effect of the number of cells on the analytical signal for different target (Caco2) and control cells (THP-1) proportions for; **(a)** simultaneous labeling with AuNPs/anti-EpCAM and **(b)** simultaneous labeling with AuNPs/anti-CEA. 100% corresponds to a cell amount of 5×10^4 . **(c)** Calibration plot for increasing number of Caco2 cells (in the absence of THP-1) with simultaneous labeling with AuNPs/anti-CEA.

Supporting Information

Simple monitoring of cancer cells using nanoparticles

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MATERIALS AND METHODS

Cell culture. The human colon adenocarcinoma cell line Caco2 was used as a model CTC. Caco2 cells (European Collection of Cell Cultures (ECACC), No: 86010202) were maintained in Earle's Minimal Essential Medium (MEM) supplemented with 10% (v/v) fetal bovine serum (FBS) and 2 mM L-glutamine in a humidified incubator (5% CO₂ at 37°C). Prior to each experiment, Caco2 cells were trypsinized in order to detach them from the culture flask. Human monocytes (THP-1 cell line from ECACC, No: 88081201), which grow in suspension, were used as blank and cultivated in RPMI medium supplemented with 10% FBS (5% CO₂ at 37°C). Culture media and supplements from PAA LaboratoriesGmBh.

Synthesis and biofunctionalization of gold nanoparticles. The 20-nm AuNPs were synthesized by an adapted method of the one pioneered by Turkevich *et al*²⁶. The glass material was washed overnight with freshly prepared Aqua Regia solution (1 part nitric acid: 3 parts hydrochloric acid). The Aqua Regia solution was then washed off thoroughly four times with MilliQ water. A total of 50 mL of 0.01% Hydrogen tetrachloroaurate (III) trihydrate (Sigma-Aldrich) prepared in MilliQ water was heated under vigorous stirring and 1.25mL of 1% trisodium citrate (Sigma-Aldrich) prepared in MilliQ water was added quickly to the solution when the temperature reached 98°C. When the solution turned deep red, indicating the formation of gold nanoparticles, it was left cooling down under stirring. In this way, a dispersed solution of near 20-nm AuNPs was obtained. Two different proteins, EpCAM (Epithelial Cell Adhesion Molecule) and CEA (Carcinoembryonic Antigen), both expressed by Caco2 cells, were used as targets for AuNPs labeling. Rabbit polyclonal anti-EpCAM (D01P, Abnova) or mouse monoclonal (1C7) anti-CEA (Ab10039, Abcam) antibodies were used for each biofunctionalization in order to create two different labels suitable for the electrochemical detection. The conjugation of AuNPs to anti-EpCAM or anti-CEA antibodies was performed according to the following procedure, previously optimized by our group.^{19,20} Briefly, 1 mL of 3 nM AuNPs suspension, with the pH corrected to 8.5 with Borate Buffer (BB; pH 9, 0.01M), was mixed with 100 µL of a 100 µg/mL antibody solution and incubated at 25°C for 20 min with

gentle stirring. Subsequently, a blocking step with 5% BSA (Sigma-Aldrich) for 20 min at 25°C was undertaken. Finally, two centrifugation steps at 14000 rpm and 5°C for 20 min were carried out in order to remove the free antibody, and the AuNPs/antibody conjugates were reconstituted in 0.1M PBS-0.1% BSA solution and kept at 4°C. To verify that the free antibody was removed from the conjugates solution, the supernatants from each centrifugation step were inspected using UV/Vis spectroscopy. Buffer compounds from Sigma-Aldrich.

Biofunctionalization of Superparamagnetic Tosylactivated microbeads (MBs).

Superparamagnetic microbeads (M280 Tosylactivated, Dynal-Biotech) are uniform polystyrene beads with a magnetic core, coated with a polyurethane layer. The surface of these beads is modified with sulphonyl ester groups that can react covalently with proteins or other ligands containing amino or sulfhydryl groups.

EpCAM glycoprotein was used as a target for MB capture, and mouse monoclonal anti-EpCAM (Ab8601, Abcam) was chosen to create biofunctionalized MBs for CTCs capture. The functionalization was performed by following the manufacturer recommended instructions. Briefly, the MBs (2 μ L, stock solution) were washed with 0.1M BB pH9.5 and resuspended in 200 μ L of 0.1M BB pH9.5 to achieve a concentration of 2×10^7 MB/mL. An excess of mouse monoclonal anti-EpCAM antibody (20 μ g) was then incubated with the MB suspension with gentle agitation (37°C, 2h) in 0.1M BB pH9.5. The MBs/anti-EpCAM conjugates were then separated from solution, washed with 0.1M BB pH9.5, and blocked with 0.01M PBS-0.5% BSA solution pH7.4 (37°C, 2h). Afterwards, MBs/anti-EpCAM conjugates were separated from blocking solution, washed and resuspended in 0.01M PBS -0.1% BSA pH7.4, and stored at 4°C until needed. Buffer compounds from Sigma-Aldrich.

Labeling of Caco2 cells with AuNPs/antibody conjugates. Different amounts of Caco2 cells (from 0 to 5×10^4), resuspended in 0.01 M PBS-0.1% BSA, were incubated with 50 μ L ($\sim 9 \times 10^{10}$ AuNPs) of AuNPs/anti-CEA or AuNPs/anti-EpCAM conjugates (30 min, 25°C, with agitation). After

removing the excess of AuNPs with three centrifugation-washing steps (5 min, 1000 rpm), cells were resuspended in 0.01M PBS -0.1% BSA.

Capture of Caco2 cells by MB/anti-EpCAM and simultaneous labeling with AuNPs/antibody.

Different amounts of Caco2 cells (from 0 to 5×10^4), resuspended in 0.01M PBS-0.1% BSA, were simultaneously incubated with MB/anti-EpCAM (2.5 μ L) and AuNPs/antibody (50 μ L, $\sim 9 \times 10^{10}$ AuNPs) conjugates. After incubation (30 min, 25°C, with agitation), captured cells were separated from the solution using a magnetic separation platform. They were washed two times to eliminate the excess of antibody functionalized AuNPs, resuspended in 0.01M PBS, and then analysed.

Flow cytometry and microscopy analyses of cell interaction with anti-EpCAM modified MBs

and biofunctionalized AuNPs. Caco2 cells (2×10^5 resuspended in 0.01M PBS-0.1%BSA) were incubated with MBs/anti-EpCAM (2.5 μ L) or AuNPs/anti-EpCAM (50 μ L, $\sim 9 \times 10^{10}$ AuNPs) conjugates, or simultaneously with of AuNPs/anti-EpCAM (50 μ L, $\sim 9 \times 10^{10}$ AuNPs) and MB/anti-EpCAM (2.5 μ L) conjugates. After incubation (30 min, 25°C, with agitation), labeled cells were separated from solution using a magnetic separation platform (when MBs were used) or by centrifugation (when no MBs were used). They were washed two times to eliminate the excess of antibody functionalized AuNPs, and redispersed in 0.01M PBS.

Finally, cells were incubated (30 min, 4°C) with the secondary antibody, which was different for cytometry (APC-conjugated anti-rabbit antibody, sc3846, Santa Cruz) than for microscopy (FITC-conjugated anti-rabbit antibody, F0382, Sigma) analyses. Controls were performed with citrate modified AuNPs (without anti-EpCAM antibody), and also with AuNPs conjugated to another rabbit polyclonal anti-EpCAM antibody (ab65052, Abcam) that proved to be non-specific to Caco2 cells. In cytometry analysis, the isotype controls were also performed using anti-Human IgG1 isotype non-specific to EpCAM.

Flow cytometry analysis of cells was undertaken with a BD FACSCalibur, Becton Dickinson, and optical microscopy analysis with an Olympus IX85 motorized inverted microscope.

Fabrication of screen-printed carbon electrodes (SPCEs). The electrochemical transducers were homemade screen-printed carbon electrodes (SPCEs) consisting of three electrodes in a single strip: working electrode (WE), reference electrode (RE) and counter electrode (CE). The full size of the sensor strip was 29mm x 6.7mm, and the WE diameter was 3mm. The fabrication of the SPCEs was carried out in three steps in the semi-automatic screen-printing machine DEK248 (DEK International, Switzerland), using a different stencil, with the corresponding patterns, for each layer. First, a graphite layer (Electrodag 423SS carbon ink for WE and CE) was printed onto the polyester sheet (Autostat HT5, McDermid Autotype, UK). After curing for 30 min at 95°C, a second layer was printed with silver/silver chloride ink (Electrodag 6037SS for the RE). After another curing for 30 min at 95°C, the insulating layer was printed using insulating ink (Minico 7000 Blue, Acheson Industries, The Netherlands) to protect the contacts and define the sample interaction area. Finally, the SPCEs were cured again at 95°C for 20 min.

Electrochemical detection of AuNPs labeled Caco2 cells by chronoamperometry. The electrochemical quantification of Caco2 cells based on the electrocatalytic detection of biofunctionalized AuNPs was performed in 1M HCl by chronoamperometry. All measurements were carried out at room temperature with a working volume of 50µL, which was enough to cover the three electrodes contained in the homemade SPCE used as electrotransducer, connected to the potentiostat (µAutolab II, Echo Chemie, The Netherlands) by a homemade edge connector module.

Different amounts of Caco2 cells (from 0 to 5×10^4) labeled with the AuNPs/antibody conjugates were placed (25µL) onto the working electrode surface and HCl was added to obtain a 50µL drop. Chronoamperograms were registered applying a constant voltage of -1.0V during 60 seconds. The analytical signal of each sample was obtained by the subtraction of the blank (the absolute of both current values registered at 50 seconds).

Electrochemical detection of AuNPs labeled Caco2 cells in the presence of interferent cells. To demonstrate the specificity of the detection, a selectivity test was performed. CTCs circulate in the blood flow among thousands of other human cells and their detection must be selective enough to avoid false positive results. Thus, a circulating cell line (monocytes) was chosen to simulate the possible interference caused by other cells in our Caco2 cell detection.

A total of 5×10^4 cells were prepared by mixing Caco2 cells in suspension with monocytes (THP-1 cells) at different proportions (100, 70, 50 and 20% of Caco2 cells). They were then simultaneously incubated with $50 \mu\text{L}$ of AuNPs/antibody conjugate and $2.5 \mu\text{L}$ of MBs/anti-EpCAM (30 min, 25°C with slow agitation). After removing the excess of AuNPs by magnetic separation and two subsequent washing steps with 0.01M PBS, samples were analyzed by the electrochemical method described above.

Sample preparation for Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) analysis. Caco2 cell samples, in the presence or absence of THP-1 control cells, were prepared following the same protocol. A suspension of 2×10^5 cells incubated with anti-EpCAM functionalized-AuNPs and/or MBs/anti-EpCAM conjugates, was fixed with 2.5% glutaraldehyde in 0.1M cacodilate buffer, during 1 h at 25°C . After each of the following steps, cells labeled with AuNPs/anti-EpCAM conjugates and attached to MBs were recovered by magnetic separation, whereas cells labeled only with AuNPs/anti-EpCAM conjugates were recovered by centrifugation. After removing the supernatant solution, pellets were dehydrated sequentially in ethanol increasing series (30, 50 and 96 %, 5 min each, 25°C). To complete the dehydration process, samples were incubated three times in 100% ethanol (5 min, 25°C), and finally resuspended in hexamethyldisilazane (Sigma-Aldrich) solution and kept at 4°C until analysis. The volume of all reagents used was always 10x the pellet volume, and slow agitation was performed to promote a better diffusion. Prior to SEM analysis (Merlin®FE-SEM, Zeiss), $4 \mu\text{L}$ of each sample were deposited onto a $0.5 \times 0.5 \text{mm}$ silicon dioxide wafer placed over a typical SEM sample holder. This protocol avoids the use of metallization steps while maintaining the cellular structure intact, and allows a direct visualization of small metallic nanoparticles onto the cell surface.

Figure S1. TEM images of AuNPs, before (a) and after (b) biofunctionalization with anti-EpCAM antibody; (c) UV-Vis spectra of AuNPs samples before (upper curve) and after (lower curve) biofunctionalization with anti-EpCAM.

Figure S2. Flow Cytometry analysis performed after 30 minute incubations, as described in the methods section. After appropriate forward and sideward scatter gating, the Caco2 cells were evaluated using PE and FITC signals (a) Caco2 cells incubated with AuNPs/monoclonal-anti-EpCAM without fluorescent-tagged secondary antibody. The histogram count indicates that the cells labeled with AuNPs/anti-EpCAM do not show autofluorescence perceived by the cytometer detector. (b) Caco2 cells incubated with polyclonal-anti-EpCAM with fluorescent-tagged secondary antibody. The histogram count indicates that the cells were weakly labeled with this anti-EpCAM antibody.

Figure S3. Flow Cytometry analysis performed after 30 minute incubations, as described in the methods section. Caco2 cells incubated with MBs/monoclonal-anti-EpCAM (4.5mm) without fluorescent-tagged secondary antibody. After appropriate forward and sideward scatter gating, the Caco2 cells were evaluated using PE and FITC signals. The histogram count indicates that the cells labeled with the MBs/anti-EpCAM show autofluorescence perceived by the cytometer detector. The presence of several “sharp peaks” may indicate a non-homogeneous labeling and the presence of cell aggregates besides the presence of a considerable amount of unlabeled cells.

Figure S4. Fluorescence microscopy images at bright field (a and b) and fluorescence mode (c) of Caco2 cells incubated with MBs/monoclonal-anti-EpCAM (4.5mm), without fluorescent-tagged secondary antibody (the MBs/anti-EpCAM show autofluorescence). In both fields it is possible to observe the aggregation of cells due to the presence of MBs.

Figure S5. Flow Cytometry analysis performed after 30 minute incubations, as described in the methods section. After appropriate forward and sideward scatter gating, the Caco2 cells were evaluated using PE, APC, and FITC signals. (a, b) Caco2 cells simultaneously incubated with MBs/monoclonal-anti-EpCAM (4.5 μ m) and AuNPs/anti-EpCAM analyzed using APC-tagged secondary antibody. Caco2 cells with MBs/Cell ratio of 14:1 (a) and with MBs/Cell ratio of 2:1(b). Both the PE/APC signal analysis and the histogram count indicate that there is a considerable higher amount of cells in (b) and that they are more homogeneously labeled.

Figure S6. Flow Cytometry analysis performed after 30 minute incubations, as described in the methods section. After appropriate forward and sideward scatter gating, the Caco2 cells were evaluated using PE, APC and FITC signals. (a) Caco2 cells incubated with AuNPs/anti-EpCAM analyzed using APC-tagged secondary antibody. The PE/APC analysis indicates that the cells are totally labeled by AuNPs/anti-EpCAM and in the histogram count there is no evidence of any cell aggregation. (b) Caco2 cells simultaneously incubated with MBs/monoclonal-anti-EpCAM (2.8mm) and AuNPs/anti-EpCAM analyzed using APC-tagged secondary antibody. The cells are more homogeneously labeled by the MBs/anti-EpCAM since only one “peak” is present in the histogram count. The PE/APC signal indicates that similarly with (a) the cells are also labeled with AuNPs/anti-EpCAM.

Figure S7. Scanning electron microscopy. Images of Caco2 (a) and THP-1 cells (c); Higher magnification images using scattered (b,d) and backscattered (b',d') electrons mode. (e) Image of Caco2 cell after labeling with AuNPs/anti-EpCAM; Higher magnification images using scattered (f) and backscattered (f') electrons mode, showing AuNPs distributed along the cell plasma membrane

Figure S8. Scanning electron microscopy. (a) Image of Caco2 cell captured by MBs/anti-EpCAM; Higher magnification images using scattered (b) and backscattered (b') electrons mode. (c) Image of Caco2 cell captured by MBs/antiEpcAM and labeled with AuNPs/anti-EpCAM; Higher magnification images using scattered (d) and backscattered (d') electrons mode, showing AuNPs distributed along the cell plasma membrane.